

Supplementary Figures for

Cloning vectors and contamination issues in pangolin metagenomic datasets raise concerns over pangolin CoV genome authenticity

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This PDF file includes:

Figures S1 to S79

Supp Fig. S1. Spearman correlation matrix for selected viruses aligned to all SRAs shown in Fig. 2. Plotted using matplotlib and seaborn.

Supp Fig. S2. Number of reads in WGS SRA's in PRJNA573298 aligned to virus genomes using bowtie2. Log₁₀ y scale. See Supp. Info. 0.4 for accession code lookup.

Supp Fig. S3. Percent coverage by reads in WGS SRA's in PRJNA573298 aligned to virus genomes using bowtie2. See Supp. Info. 0.4 for accession code lookup.

Supp. Fig. S4. Pooled SRA's SRR10168376-78 (Lung09, Lung08 and Lung07) aligned to MT121216.1 using bwa mem and plotted in IGV. Coverage is shown in grey, scaled 0-22.

Supp. Fig. S5. Read coverage for pooled reads from SRR1068373-93 aligned to Parus major densovirus isolate PmdDNV-JL (NC_031450.1), aligned with bowtie2, plotted in IGV.

Supp Fig. S6. De novo assembled contigs for each SRA in PRJNA573298 were analysed against the nt database using MagicBLAST, counts of contigs aligning to selected taxa groupings are shown.

Supp Fig. S7. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA573298 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'manis javanica' or 'manis pentadactyla'.

Supp Fig. S8. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA573298 using MagicBLAST against the nt database with description including the terms 'mulatta', 'troglodytes', 'pongo', 'papio', 'mandrillus', 'cercocebus', 'gelada' or 'chlorocebus'.

Supp Fig. S9. Contigs identified in PRJNA573298 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'vector', counts per SRA.

Supp Fig. S10. Contigs identified in PRJNA573298 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'virus', and excluding 'retrovirus', counts per SRA.

Supp Fig. S11. Spearman correlation coefficient matrix for reads aligned to selected viruses using bowtie2, as well as human and mouse contig counts generated through *de novo* assembly. Read data from each SRA in PRJNA573298 was used.

Supp. Fig. S11. Read coverage for pooled reads from SRR10168373-93 aligned to Cloning vector pcDNA3.1₊ (MN996867.1), aligned with bwa mem, plotted in IGV. Coverage track shown in log scale.

Supp. Fig. S13. Consensus from pooled SRR10168373-93 reads (Supp. Fig. S11) aligned to Cloning vector pcDNA3.1₊ (MN996867.1), plotted in Addgene sequence analyzer.

Lam et al. 2020 (PRJNA606875)

Supp Fig. S14. Distribution of 83 75nt reads with an identical match and 132 75nt long reads with a single nucleotide difference in the GD/P2S dataset (SRR11093265) to SARS-CoV-2 Wuhan-Hu-1 (NC_045512.2).

Supp Fig. S15. Reads in each SRA in PRJNA606875 were aligned using bowtie2 to microbes identified using fastv. Number of aligned reads are coloured using a log scale. Note that the read alignments to NC_045512.2 for SRR11093266-71 were only partial.

Supp Fig. S16. Reads in each SRA in PRJNA606875 were aligned using bowtie2 to microbes identified using fastv. Percent coverage of each genome is shown. Note that the read alignments to NC_045512.2 for SRR11093266-71 were only partial.

Supp Fig. S17. De novo assembled contigs for each WGS SRA in PRJNA606875 were grouped and counted.

Supp Fig. S18. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA606875 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'virus' and excluding 'retrovirus'.

Supp Fig. S19. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA606875 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'manis javanica' or 'manis pentadactyla'.

Supp Fig. S20. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA606875 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'human' or 'homo sapiens'.

Supp Fig. S21. Number of reads aligned for cleaned reads for each WGS SRA in PRJNA607174 aligned to selected microbial sequences using bowtie2. Log₁₀ colour scale.

Supp Fig. S22. Coverage percent for cleaned reads for each WGS SRA in PRJNA607174 aligned to selected microbial sequences using bowtie2.

Supp Fig. S23. Spearman correlation coefficient matrix for reads aligned to selected viruses using bowtie2, as well as human and mouse contig counts generated through de novo assembly. Read data from each SRA in PRJNA607174 with the exception of SRR13053879 was used.

	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SjqD chromosome, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	2339309	CP047586.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SjqM chromosome, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	2339229	CP046955.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SjqH chromosome, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	2339262	CP046731.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain sjqB chromosome, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	2339548	CP046732.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVMG48_truncated-R, complete sequence	Expression vect...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	8938	MN551093.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVMG47_truncated-L, complete sequence	Expression vect...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	8938	MN551092.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG307_truncated, complete sequence	Expression vect...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	8918	MN551091.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG185_w2-y1, complete sequence	Expression vect...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	8958	MN551090.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG316_vasa-Cas9, complete sequence	Expression vect...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	14339	MN551089.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Suicide vector pMC3752, complete sequence	Suicide vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	10135	MN186288.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	E. coli-T. kodakarensis shuttle vector pTNTnpE, complete sequence	E. coli-T. kodaka...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	9026	MG920814.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	E. coli-T. kodakarensis shuttle vector pTNAg, complete sequence	E. coli-T. kodaka...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	8189	MG920813.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigmaE, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	2339255	CP020356.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0302_Cq-U6-1_2xBbsI-gRNA-Loop, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	4820	MW925707.2
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0146_Cq-U6-1_2xBbsI-gRNA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	4810	MW925700.2
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0303_Cq-U6-6_2xBbsI-gRNA-Loop, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	4616	MW925708.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0109_CC-U6-3-w5_GFP_wHAs_O, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	9522	MW925706.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0252_Cq-vasa-Cas9_cdHAs_O, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	16587	MW925705.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0149_Cq-U6-6_2xBbsI-gRNA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	4606	MW925703.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0218_Cq-U6-4_2xBbsI-gRNA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	5789	MW925702.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0217_Cq-U6-2b_2xBbsI-gRNA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	6431	MW925701.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0212_Cq-nanos-cas9, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	13640	MW925699.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0213_Cq-vasa-Cas9, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	11242	MW925698.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0193_Cq-RpH0-Cas9, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	12349	MW925697.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0173_Cq-Actin5c-Cas9, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	16134	MW925696.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVG363_Aste-U6a-Swap4-gRNA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	4862	MW030450.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gibberella moniliformis p450-4 gene for ent-kaurene oxidase, exons 1-4, strain A-00149	Fusarium verticil...	828	828	100%	0.0	99.78%	3556	AM946177.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain phoP, complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	825	825	98%	0.0	100.00%	2339296	CP019768.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pXF20pemIK-GW, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	825	916	98%	0.0	100.00%	7744	KX036765.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pPS2305, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	825	825	98%	0.0	100.00%	4381	KF532954.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pCR2.1-sacB, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	825	825	98%	0.0	100.00%	5522	KC577242.1

Supp. Fig. S24. Section 539-1000nt from GD1 amplicon read 0089_31320022801126_24-6-1-4-jy_M13F.ab1 (Read id '12' in Supp info 0.3) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database using default parameters.

Cloning vector pVMG0193_Cq-Rpl40-Cas9, complete sequence

Sequence ID: [MW925697.1](#) Length: 12349 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 3216 to 3678 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#)

[▼ Next Match](#) [▲ Previous Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
828 bits(917)	0.0	462/463(99%)	1/463(0%)	Plus/Minus
Query Sbjct	539 3678	AGGGC - AATTCCAGCACACTGGCGGCCGTTACTAGTGGATCCGAGCTCGGTACCAAGCTTG.....		597 3619
Query Sbjct	598 3618	GGCGTAATCATGGTCATAGCTGTTTCCTGTGTGAAATTGTTATCCGCTCACAATTCCACA		657 3559
Query Sbjct	658 3558	CAACATACGAGCCGGAAGCATAAAGTGTAAAGCCTGGGGTGCCTAATGAGTGAGCTAACT		717 3499
Query Sbjct	718 3498	CACATTAATTGCGTTGCGCTCACTGCCCGCTTCCAGTCGGGAAACCTGTCGTGCCAGCT		777 3439
Query Sbjct	778 3438	GCATTAATGAATCGGCCAACGCGCGGGGAGAGGCGGTTTTCGTATTGGGCGCTCTTCCGC		837 3379
Query Sbjct	838 3378	TTCTCTCGCTCACTGACTCGCTGCGCTCGGTCGTTTCGGCTGCGGCGAGCGGTATCAGCTCA		897 3319
Query Sbjct	898 3318	CTCAAAGGCGGTAATACGGTTATCCACAGAATCAGGGGATAACGCAGGAAAGAACATGTG		957 3259
Query Sbjct	958 3258	AGCAAAAGGCCAGCAAAAGGCCAGGAACCGTAAAAAGGCCGCG	1000 3216	

[Download](#) [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) Sort by:

Cloning vector pXF20pemIK-GW, complete sequence

Sequence ID: [KX036765.1](#) Length: 7744 Number of Matches: 2

Range 1: 617 to 1073 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#)

[▼ Next Match](#) [▲ Previous Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
825 bits(914)	0.0	457/457(100%)	0/457(0%)	Plus/Minus
Query Sbjct	544 1073	AATTCCAGCACACTGGCGGCCGTTACTAGTGGATCCGAGCTCGGTACCAAGCTTGGCGTA		603 1014
Query Sbjct	604 1013	ATCATGGTCATAGCTGTTTCCTGTGTGAAATTGTTATCCGCTCACAATCCACACAACAT		663 954
Query Sbjct	664 953	ACGAGCCGGAAGCATAAAGTGTAAAGCCTGGGGTGCCTAATGAGTGAGCTAACTCACATT		723 894
Query Sbjct	724 893	AATTGCGTTGCGCTCACTGCCCGCTTCCAGTCGGGAAACCTGTCGTGCCAGCTGCATTA		783 834
Query Sbjct	784 833	ATGAATCGGCCAACGCGCGGGGAGAGGCGGTTTTCGTATTGGGCGCTCTTCCGCTTCTC		843 774
Query Sbjct	844 773	GCTCACTGACTCGCTGCGCTCGGTCGTTTCGGCTGCGGCGAGCGGTATCAGCTCACTCAA		903 714
Query Sbjct	904 713	GGCGGTAATACGGTTATCCACAGAATCAGGGGATAACGCAGGAAAGAACATGTGAGCAA		963 654
Query Sbjct	964 653	AGGCCAGCAAAAGGCCAGGAACCGTAAAAAGGCCGCG	1000 617	

Supp. Fig. S25. Section 539-1000nt from GD1 amplicon read 0089_31320022801126_24-6-1-4-jy_M13F.ab1 (Read id '12' in Supp info 0.3) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database using default parameters, selected alignments.

Program **BLASTN** [Citation](#) ?

Database **nt** [See details](#) ?

Query ID **lc|Query_30605**

Description **None**

Molecule type **dna**

Query Length **81**

Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) ?

Organism *only top 20 will appear*

Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name

[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to

E value to

Query Coverage to

Filter **Reset**

Descriptions Graphic Summary Alignments Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download ? **New** Select columns ? Show **100** ?

select all *4 sequences selected*

[GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) **New** [MSA Viewer](#)

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	6484	MH752994.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	6239	MH752993.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	5830	MH752992.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Aeromonas caviae strain 7F8-3 class 1 integron fluoroquinolone acetylating aminoglycoside-(6')-N-acetyltrans...	Aeromonas caviae	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	1115	KR868995.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Aeromonas caviae strain 7F2-3 class 1 integron fluoroquinolone acetylating aminoglycoside-(6')-N-acetyltrans...	Aeromonas caviae	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	1714	KR868994.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Arcanobacterium pyogenes strain RY-H06-3 class I In I-1 Integron, partial sequence	Trueperella pyo...	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	1214	FJ655778.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector pEASY-T1, complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	129	129	87%	3e-26	100.00%	3928	EU233623.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Danio rerio cDNA, clone cssl:d0658	Danio rerio	126	126	88%	3e-25	98.61%	1656	CU638782.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Uncultured Methanococcus sp., partial 16S rRNA gene, clone ATOS Iris7 Rainbow 8A	uncultured Meth...	126	126	88%	3e-25	98.61%	972	AJ969479.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Uncultured Methanocaldococcus sp., partial 16S rRNA gene, clone ATOS Iris7 Rainbow 58A	uncultured Meth...	126	126	88%	3e-25	98.61%	848	AJ969478.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Uncultured Archaeoglobales archaeon partial 16S rRNA gene, clone ATOS Iris7 Rainbow 4A	uncultured Arch...	126	126	88%	3e-25	98.61%	847	AJ969477.1

Supp. Fig. S26. Section 1-81nt from GD1 amplicon read 0089_31320022801126_24-6-1-4-jy_M13F.ab1 (Read id '12' in Supp info 0.3) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database using default parameters.

Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII, complete sequence

Sequence ID: [MH752994.1](#) Length: **6484** Number of Matches: **1**

Range 1: **2853 to 2923** [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) ? [Next Match](#) [Previous Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
129 bits(142)	3e-26	71/71(100%)	0/71(0%)	Plus/Minus

```

Query 11  TATAGGGCGAATTGGGCCCTCTAGATGCATGCTCGAGCGGCCGCCAGTGTGATGGATATC 70
Sbjct 2923 TATAGGGCGAATTGGGCCCTCTAGATGCATGCTCGAGCGGCCGCCAGTGTGATGGATATC 2864

Query 71  TGCAGAATTGC 81
Sbjct 2863 TGCAGAATTGC 2853
  
```

Supp. Fig. S27. Section 1-81nt from GD1 amplicon read 0089_31320022801126_24-6-1-4-jy_M13F.ab1 (Read id '12' in Supp info 0.3) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database using default parameters showing alignment to cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII.

Program **BLASTN** [Citation](#) ▼

Database **nt** [See details](#) ▼

Query ID **lcl|Query_21167**

Description **None**

Molecule type **dna**

Query Length **554**

Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) ?

Organism *only top 20 will appear* exclude

Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name

[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to

E value to

Query Coverage to

Filter **Reset**

Descriptions | Graphic Summary | Alignments | Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download New Select columns Show ?

select all *100 sequences selected* [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) New [MSA Viewer](#)

	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII	1000	1000	100%	0.0	100.00%	6484	MH752994.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA	1000	1000	100%	0.0	100.00%	6239	MH752993.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble	1000	1000	100%	0.0	100.00%	5830	MH752992.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-T1 complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-T1	998	998	99%	0.0	100.00%	3928	EU233623.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain sigC chromosome complete genome	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis	994	994	100%	0.0	99.82%	2338957	CP047926.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigD chromosome complete genome	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis	994	994	100%	0.0	99.82%	2339309	CP047586.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigM chromosome complete genome	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis	994	994	100%	0.0	99.82%	2339229	CP046955.1

Supp. Fig. S28. Section 1-554nt from GD1 amplicon read 0030_31320022801096_(24-2-3-jy)_[M13R].ab1 (Read id '35' in Supp info 0.3) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database using default parameters.

Program **BLASTN** [Citation](#) ▼

Database **nt** [See details](#) ▼

Query ID **lcl|Query_661**

Description **None**

Molecule type **dna**

Query Length **613**

Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) ?

Organism *only top 20 will appear* exclude

Type common name, binomial, taxid or group name

[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to

E value to

Query Coverage to

Filter **Reset**

Descriptions | Graphic Summary | Alignments | Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download New Select columns Show ?

select all *100 sequences selected* [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) New [MSA Viewer](#)

	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-T1 complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-T1	1082	1082	98%	0.0	99.83%	3928	EU233623.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII	1000	1093	98%	0.0	100.00%	6484	MH752994.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA	1000	1091	98%	0.0	100.00%	6239	MH752993.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble	1000	1091	98%	0.0	100.00%	5830	MH752992.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pHR-Ech_0230-tuf-aadA complete sequence	Cloning vector pHR-Ech_0230-tuf-aadA	999	1084	98%	0.0	99.82%	7173	MF068805.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVG363_Aste-U6a-Swap4-gRNA complete sequence	Cloning vector pVG363_Aste-U6a-Swap4-...	999	1086	98%	0.0	99.82%	4862	MW030450.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVG362_Aste-U6a-Swap3-gRNA complete sequence	Cloning vector pVG362_Aste-U6a-Swap3-...	999	1086	98%	0.0	99.82%	4861	MW030449.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Neurospora cloning vector pTH1111.1 complete sequence	Neurospora cloning vector pTH1111.1	999	1084	98%	0.0	99.82%	7308	JF749200.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVMG48_truncated-R complete sequence	Expression vector pVMG48_truncated-R	998	1083	98%	0.0	99.29%	8938	MN551093.1

Supp. Fig. S29. Misaligned sections after aligning to GD_1 genome from read ids '21' and '25' (Supp info 0.3) were spliced then analyzed using BLASTN against the nt database.

Cloning vector pEASY-T1, complete sequence

Sequence ID: [EU233623.1](#) Length: 3928 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 244 to 846 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#)

▼ [Next Match](#) ▲ [Previous Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
1082 bits(1199)	0.0	603/604(99%)	1/604(0%)	Plus/Minus
Query 1	GTCCACTATTAAGAACGTGGACTCCAACGTCAAAGGGCGAAAAACCGTCTATCAGGGCG	60		
Sbjct 846	787		
Query 61	ATGGCCCACTACGTGAACCATCACCTAATCAAGTTTTTTGGGGTCGAGGTGCCGTAAG	120		
Sbjct 786	727		
Query 121	CACTAAATCGGAACCCTAAAGGGAGCCCCGATTTAGAGCTTGACGGGGAAAGCCGGCGA	180		
Sbjct 726	667		
Query 181	ACGTGGCGAGAAAGGAAGGGAAGAAAGCGAAAGGAGCGGGCGCTAGGGCGCTGGCAAGTG	240		
Sbjct 666	607		
Query 241	TAGCGGTCACGCTGCGCGTAACCACCACACCCGCCGCGCTTAATGCGCCGCTACAGGGCG	300		
Sbjct 606	547		
Query 301	CGTCCATTCGCCATTCAGGCTGCGCAACTGTTGGGAAGGGCGATCGGTGCGGGCCTCTTC	360		
Sbjct 546	487		
Query 361	GCTATTACGCCAGCTGGCGAAAGGGGGATGTGCTGCAAGGCGATTAAGTTGGGTAACGCC	420		
Sbjct 486	427		
Query 421	AGGGTTTTCCAGTCACGACGTTGTA AACGACGGCCAGTGAATTGTAATACGACTCACT	480		
Sbjct 426	367		
Query 481	ATAGGGCGAATTGGGCCCTCTAGATGCATGCTCGAGCGGCCGCCAGTGTGATGGATATCT	540		
Sbjct 366	307		
Query 541	GCAGAATTGCCCTTAAGGGCAATTCAGCACACTGGCGGCCGTTACTAGTGGATCCGAGC	600		
Sbjct 306-	248		
Query 601	TCGG	604		
Sbjct 247	244		

Supp. Fig. S30. Misaligned sections after aligning to GD_1 genome from read ids '21' and '25' (Supp info 0.3) were spliced then analyzed using BLASTN against the nt database and found to have highest identity to the pEASY-T1 cloning vector.

Supp. Fig. S31. Pooled reads from SRAs in Xiao et al. (2020) Extended Table 3 coverage aligned to GD_1 genome with bowtie2 (grey, top track); GD1 amplicon reads aligned to GD_1 genome with bwa mem: coverage track (grey), and read track, coloured by read direction (pink/blue) and mismatched nucleotides (strong colours). Abundant mismatched sections are evident at read ends.

Supp. Fig. S32. Contig K79_3 obtained after de novo assembly of SRR13053879, plotted in addgene in circular layout.

Supp. Fig. S33. Contig K79_5 (from *de novo* assembly of SRR13053879) plotted in addgene.

Supp. Fig. S34. Contigs obtained after *de novo* assembly of SRR13053879 were aligned to the GD_1 genome sequence, contig K79_3 was located at the 5' most end of the GD_1 genome and plotted here in IGV.

Program **BLASTN** [Citation](#)
 Database **nt** [See details](#)
 Query ID **lcl|Query_519869**
 Description **None**
 Molecule type **dna**
 Query Length **1022**
 Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#)

Organism only top 20 will appear exclude

[+ Add organism](#)

Percent Identity to
E value to
Query Coverage to

Filter **Reset**

Descriptions | Graphic Summary | Alignments | Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download Select columns Show 100

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	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII .complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/hptII	982	1126	61%	0.0	99.64%	6484	MH752994.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA .complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/aadA	982	1124	61%	0.0	99.64%	6239	MH752993.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble .complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-tub/ble	980	1122	60%	0.0	100.00%	5830	MH752992.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEASY-T1 .complete sequence	Cloning vector pEASY-T1	978	1120	60%	0.0	100.00%	3928	EU233623.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pEM021 .complete sequence	Cloning vector pEM021	976	1112	61%	0.0	99.64%	6022	MK431398.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Artificial vector pJL531 .complete sequence	Artificial vector pJL531	976	1112	61%	0.0	99.64%	5716	JF295006.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Artificial vector pJL529 .complete sequence	Artificial vector pJL529	976	1112	61%	0.0	99.64%	6799	JF295005.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Artificial vector pJL517 .complete sequence	Artificial vector pJL517	976	1112	61%	0.0	99.64%	6612	JF295004.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain sigC chromosome .complete genome	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis	976	976	53%	0.0	99.82%	2338957	CP047926.1
<input type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pHR-res-Ech_0379-Amtr-mCh-Gent .complete sequence	Cloning vector pHR-res-Ech_0379-Amtr-m...	976	1111	60%	0.0	99.82%	8345	MF068807.1

Supp. Fig. S35. Contig K79_3 obtained after *de novo* assembly of SRR13053879 was analysed using BLASTN against the nt database.

Supp. Fig. S36. Contig K79_3 obtained after *de novo* assembly of SRR13053879 was analysed using BLASTN against the nt database. Alignment distribution, GD_1 sequence located in non-matched region.

Query Length 533

Other reports [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#) [?](#) Filter Reset

Descriptions Graphic Summary Alignments Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments Download New Select columns Show 100 [?](#)

select all 100 sequences selected GenBank Graphics Distance tree of results New MSA Viewer

	Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigD chromosome complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	2339309	CP047586.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain sigB chromosome complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	2339548	CP046732.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVMG49_truncated-R_complete sequence	Expression vect...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	8938	MN551093.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVMG47_truncated-L_complete sequence	Expression vect...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	8938	MN551092.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG307_truncated_complete sequence	Expression vect...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	8918	MN551091.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG185_w2-y1_complete sequence	Expression vect...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	8958	MN551090.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Expression vector pVG316_vasa-Cas9_complete sequence	Expression vect...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	14339	MN551089.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigmaE complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	2339255	CP020356.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0109_Cq-U6-3-w5_GFP_wHAs_O_complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	9522	MW925706.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0219_Cq-U6-4_2xBbsI-gRNA_complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	5789	MW925702.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0217_Cq-U6-2b_2xBbsI-gRNA_complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	6431	MW925701.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cloning vector pVMG0193_Cq-Rpl40-Cas9_complete sequence	Cloning vector p...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	12349	MW925697.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Gibberella moniliformis p450-4 gene for ent-kaurene oxidase exons 1-4 strain A-00149	Fusarium verticil...	979	979	100%	0.0	99.81%	3556	AM946177.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigM chromosome complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	977	977	99%	0.0	99.81%	2339229	CP046955.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis strain SigH chromosome complete genome	Corynebacteriu...	977	977	99%	0.0	99.81%	2339262	CP046731.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Suicide vector pMC3752_complete sequence	Suicide vector p...	977	977	99%	0.0	99.81%	10135	MN186288.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	E_coli-T_kodakarensis shuttle vector pTNTTrpE_complete sequence	E_coli-T_kodaka...	977	977	99%	0.0	99.81%	9026	MG920814.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	E_coli-T_kodakarensis shuttle vector pTNAg_complete sequence	E_coli-T_kodaka...	977	977	99%	0.0	99.81%	8189	MG920813.1

Supp. Fig. S37. Contig K79_5 (from de novo assembly of SRR13053879) analysed using BLASTN against the nt database.

Enter Query Sequence

Enter accession number(s), gi(s), or FASTA sequence(s) [?](#) [Clear](#) Query subrange [?](#)

>k79_5 flag=0 multi=15.0000 len=533
 CAAGGGCAATCCAGCACACTGGCGCCGTACTAGTGGATCCGAGCTC
 GGTACCAAGCTTGCGTAATC
 ATGGTCATAGCTGTTTCCTGTGTGAAATTGTTATCCGCTCACAATCCACAC

From

To

Or, upload file Browse... No file selected. [?](#)

Job Title
 Enter a descriptive title for your BLAST search [?](#)

Align two or more sequences [?](#)

Choose Search Set

Database Standard databases (nr etc.): rRNA/ITS databases Genomic + transcript databases Betacoronavirus

Sequence Read Archive (SRA) [?](#)

Add organism

Enter an SRA accession (experiment, study, or submission), title, the scientific name or tax id. Only 20 top suggestions will be shown. [?](#)

Program Selection

Optimize for Highly similar sequences (megablast)
 More dissimilar sequences (discontiguous megablast)
 Somewhat similar sequences (blastn)
 Choose a BLAST algorithm [?](#)

Supp. Fig. S38. Settings for query of contig K79_5 (from de novo assembly of SRR13053879) against specific SRA's using NCBI BLASTN.

Supp. Fig. S39. NCBI BLASTN query of contig K79_5 (from de novo assembly of SRR13053879) against specific SRA's shown in MSA viewer.

Supp. Fig. S40. After de novo assembly, each contig was analyzed against the nt database using MagicBLAST. Those with sequences best matching specific animal types, as well as to viruses, vectors and mycoplasma were grouped by SRA and counts plotted.

Supp. Fig. S41. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA607174 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'manis javanica' or 'manis pentadactyla'.

Supp Fig. S42. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA607174 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'human' or 'homo sapiens'.

Supp Fig. S43. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA607174 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'mulatta', 'troglodytes', 'pongo', 'papio', 'mandrillus', 'cercocebus', 'gelada' or 'chlorocebus'.

Supp Fig. S44. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA607174 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'mus musculus'.

Supp Fig. S45. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA607174 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'canis lupus'.

Supp Fig. S46. Contigs identified using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'vector', counts per SRA.

Supp Fig. S47. Contigs identified using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'virus' and excluding 'retrovirus', counts per SRA.

Supp. Fig. S48. De novo assembled contig k141_294696 in SRR11119762 with Porcine circovirus 2 capsid protein in ORF 4738-5841bp.

Supp. Fig. S49. De novo assembled contig k141_1503693 in SRR11119764 containing hypothetical protein IM014_gp010 [African swine fever virus] and hypothetical protein IM014_gp116 [African swine fever virus] sequences.

Supp Fig. S50. Reads from all SRA's in PRJNA610466 aligned to selected genomes using bowtie2. Read counts (colour) plotted in log scale.

Supp Fig. S51. Reads from all SRA's in PRJNA610466 aligned to selected genomes using bowtie2. Percent coverage plotted as colour density.

Supp Fig. S52. Spearman correlation coefficient matrix for reads aligned to selected viruses using bowtie2, as well as human and mouse contig counts generated through de novo assembly. Read data from each SRA in PRJNA610466 was used.

Supp Fig. S53. De novo assembled contigs for each SRA in PRJNA610466 were analysed against the nt database using MagicBLAST, counts of contigs aligning to selected taxa groupings are shown.

Supp Fig. S54. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA610466 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'manis javanica' or 'manis pentadactyla'.

Supp Fig. S55. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA610466 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the terms 'human' or 'homo sapiens'.

Supp Fig. S56. Percentage of contigs per SRA identified in PRJNA610466 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'mus musculus'.

Supp Fig. S57. Contigs identified in PRJNA610466 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'vector', counts per SRA.

Supp Fig. S58. Contigs identified in PRJNA610466 using MagicBLAST against nt database with description including the term 'virus' and excluding 'retrovirus', counts per SRA.

Supp Fig. S59. SRR11306689 contig k141_9009 plotted in addgene. PacI restriction enzyme site located at lentiviral vector/*Manis Pentadactyla* genomic DNA junction.

Program: BLASTN [Citation](#)

Database: nt [See details](#)

Query ID: lcl|Query_319851

Description: None

Molecule type: dna

Query Length: 54

Other reports: [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#)

Organism: only top 20 will appear

Percent Identity: to E value: to Query Coverage: to

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Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HIV-1 isolate 2303_TMDRn_7 from USA defective genome	Human Immunodeficiency virus 1	98.7	98.7	100%	2e-17	100.00%	1250	MW754451.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HIV-1 isolate 2303_CMDRn_5 from USA defective genome	Human Immunodeficiency virus 1	98.7	98.7	100%	2e-17	100.00%	1401	MW754330.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> HIV-1 isolate 2303_CMDRn_32 from USA defective genome	Human Immunodeficiency virus 1	98.7	98.7	100%	2e-17	100.00%	4594	MW754327.1

Supp Fig. S60. NCBI BLASTN against nt database for contig k141_9009 section 1-54bp matching Human immunodeficiency virus 1.

Program: BLASTN [Citation](#)

Database: nt [See details](#)

Query ID: lcl|Query_231143

Description: None

Molecule type: dna

Query Length: 348

Other reports: [Distance tree of results](#) [MSA viewer](#)

Organism: only top 20 will appear

Percent Identity: to E value: to Query Coverage: to

[Filter](#) [Reset](#)

Descriptions | Graphic Summary | Alignments | Taxonomy

Sequences producing significant alignments [Download](#) [New Select columns](#) Show 100

select all 100 sequences selected [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) [New MSA Viewer](#)

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PREDICTED: Manis pentadactyla coiled-coil domain containing 186 (CCDC186), mRNA	Manis pentadact...	615	615	100%	2e-171	99.14%	6791	XM_036898626.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PREDICTED: Manis javanica coiled-coil domain containing 186 (CCDC186), mRNA	Manis javanica	606	606	100%	9e-169	98.56%	6794	XM_037011382.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PREDICTED: Trachypithecus francoisi coiled-coil domain containing 186 (CCDC186), transcript variant X5, mRNA	Trachypithecus f...	586	586	99%	8e-163	97.41%	2451	XM_033182081.1

Supp Fig. S61. NCBI BLASTN against nt database for contig k141_9009 section 55-402bp.

PREDICTED: Manis pentadactyla coiled-coil domain containing 186 (CCDC186), mRNA

Sequence ID: [XM_036898626.1](#) Length: 6791 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1078 to 1425 [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#)

[▼ Next Match](#) [▲ Previous Match](#)

Score	Expect	Identities	Gaps	Strand
615 bits(681)	2e-171	345/348(99%)	0/348(0%)	Plus/Plus
Query 55	TAATTAAGAAAATAAGAAGCATCAGGAGCTCTTCGTAGACATTTGTTTCAGAAAAAGACA	114		
Sbjct 1078A.AT.....	1137		
Query 115	ATTTAAGAGAAGAACTaaaaaaaaGAACAGAAAACAGAGAAGCAGCATATGAGCACAATTA	174		
Sbjct 1138	1197		
Query 175	AACAGTTAGAATCAAGAATAGAAGAACTTAGTAAAGAAGTTAAAGTTTCCAAAGATAAAC	234		
Sbjct 1198	1257		
Query 235	TAGTAGCTCAAGACTTTGCAGCTAAAAATGCAATTCAGCAGTTACACAAAGAGATGGCCC	294		
Sbjct 1258	1317		
Query 295	ATCGGATGGAACAGGCCAACAAAGAAATGTGAAGAGGCACTCCAGGAAAAAGAAGTAATGG	354		
Sbjct 1318	1377		
Query 355	TAATGAAGTATGTAAGAGGTGAGAAGGAATCATTAGACCTTCGAAAGC	402		
Sbjct 1378	1425		

Supp Fig. S62. NCBI BLASTN against nt database for contig k141_9009 section 55-402bp alignment to XM_036898626.1.

Supp Fig. S63. SRR11306689 contig k141_67383 plotted in addgene. Two regions matching Human immunodeficiency virus 1 (NC_001802.1) were identified.

ZsGreen [Reverse genetics vector pCCI-4K-SARS-CoV-2-ZsGreen]

Sequence ID: [QQK33708.1](#) Length: 232 Number of Matches: 1

Range 1: 1 to 231 [GenPept](#) [Graphics](#)

▼ Next Match ▲ Previous Match

Score	Expect	Method	Identities	Positives	Gaps
494 bits(1272)	4e-173	Compositional matrix adjust.	231/231(100%)	231/231(100%)	0/231(0%)
Query 1		MAQSKHGLTKEMTKYRMEGCVDGHKFVITGEGIGYPFKGGKQAINLCVVEGGPLPFAEDI			60
Sbjct 1		MAQSKHGLTKEMTKYRMEGCVDGHKFVITGEGIGYPFKGGKQAINLCVVEGGPLPFAEDI			60
Query 61		LSAAFMYGNRVFTEYPQDIVDYFKNSCPAGYTWDRSFLFEDGAVCICNADITVSVEENCM			120
Sbjct 61		LSAAFMYGNRVFTEYPQDIVDYFKNSCPAGYTWDRSFLFEDGAVCICNADITVSVEENCM			120
Query 121		YHESKFYGVNFPADGPMKMTDNWEPSCKEIIPVPKQILKGDVSMYLLLDKGGRLRCQ			180
Sbjct 121		YHESKFYGVNFPADGPMKMTDNWEPSCKEIIPVPKQILKGDVSMYLLLDKGGRLRCQ			180
Query 181		FDTVYKAKSVPRKMPDWHFIQHKLTREDRSDAKNQKWHLTEHAIASGSALP			231
Sbjct 181		FDTVYKAKSVPRKMPDWHFIQHKLTREDRSDAKNQKWHLTEHAIASGSALP			231

Supp. Fig. S64. ORF 3 (translated, 454 aa) from contig k141_67383 from de novo assembled sample MJS3 (SRR11306689) analyzed using NCBI BLASTX against the nr database exhibiting a 100% match for 231 aa.

Query Length 1362

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Descriptions | [Graphic Summary](#) | [Alignments](#) | [Taxonomy](#)

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select all 17 sequences selected [GenBank](#) [Graphics](#) [Distance tree of results](#) **New** [MSA Viewer](#)

Description	Scientific Name	Max Score	Total Score	Query Cover	E value	Per. Ident	Acc. Len	Accession
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mutant Zaire ebolavirus strain recEBOV-DRC2018-ZsG_complete genome	Zaire ebolavirus	1252	1252	50%	0.0	100.00%	19724	MK672825.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mutant Marburg marburgvirus strain recombinant MARV-ZsG_complete genome	Marburg marburgvirus	1252	1252	50%	0.0	100.00%	19875	MK271082.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expression vector pSOSV/ZsG-FL_complete sequence	Expression vector pS...	1252	1252	50%	0.0	100.00%	18547	MG880225.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Zaire ebolavirus strain Ebola virus/H.sapiens-rec/LBR/2014/Makona-L2014_ZsG_complete genome	Zaire ebolavirus	1252	1252	50%	0.0	100.00%	19719	KR781609.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector AGG1536_complete sequence	Cloning vector AGG1...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	14784	MN720706.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expression vector pHP87078_complete sequence	Expression vector pH...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	16841	MN380785.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expression vector pHP86491_complete sequence	Expression vector pH...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	15676	MN380782.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expression vector pHP80770_complete sequence	Expression vector pH...	1251	1430	50%	0.0	100.00%	33722	MN380778.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vector pTRE3G-Bi-ZsGreen pTRE3G-Bi-ProRIP_complete sequence	Vector pTRE3G-Bi-Zs...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	4342	MN224161.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vector pTRE3G-Bi-ZsGreen pTRE3G-Bi-b-Chain_complete sequence	Vector pTRE3G-Bi-Zs...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	3847	MN224157.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vector pTRE3G-Bi-ZsGreen pTRE3G-Bi-a-Chain_complete sequence	Vector pTRE3G-Bi-Zs...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	3961	MN224156.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Expression vector Sos_ZsG_polI-mg_complete sequence	Expression vector Sos...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	3896	MG880223.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector Hf5/le1-ITAV(OX5378)_complete sequence	Cloning vector Hf5/le1...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	9633	MT533615.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector Op/le2-ITAV(OX4585)_complete sequence	Cloning vector Op/le2...	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	10773	MT533614.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector OX4389_complete sequence	Cloning vector OX4389	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	7990	JQ352760.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector pBB189_complete sequence	Cloning vector pBB189	1251	1251	50%	0.0	100.00%	6694	JQ071441.1
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reverse genetics vector pCCI-4K-SARS-CoV-2-ZsGreen_complete sequence	Reverse genetics vect...	1249	1249	50%	0.0	100.00%	36033	MW289908.1
<input type="checkbox"/> Cloning vector AGG1201.pZsG_complete sequence	Cloning vector AGG1...	1223	1223	50%	0.0	99.13%	6075	MT119955.1

Supp. Fig. S65. 1151-2872bp (ORF 3) from contig k141_67383 from de novo assembled sample MJS3 (SRR11306689) analyzed using NCBI BLASTN against the nt database exhibiting a 100% match for 694bp to Expression vector pSOSV/ZsG-FL (Welch et al. 2018) and Zaire ebolavirus and Marburg marburgvirus strains.

Supp. Fig. S66. Simian virus 40 genome identified in contig k141_64401

Liu et al. 2020

Supp Fig. S67. Number of aligned reads to selected virus genomes in SRR13285085.

Supp Fig. S68. Percent coverage by reads for selected virus genomes in SRR13285085.

Supp. Fig. S69. Alignment using bwa mem to pangolin CoV MP789 for: coverage of pooled samples Lung07, Lung08 (top track, log scale); sample GZ1-2 (SRR13285085) showing coverage (middle track) and read depth (lower track). Plotted in IGV.

Supp. Fig. S70. Contigs after *de novo* assembly of SRR13285085 identified using MagicBLAST against nt database into taxa, counts per SRA.

Supp. Fig. S71. Alignment of amplicon dataset ‘journal_ppat_1009664_s001’ (Liu et al. 2021) to pangolin CoV MP789 (MT121216.1) using bwa mem2 (top two tracks). Alignment of amplicon dataset GD1 (SRR13053879) from BioProject PRJNA607174 is plotted for comparison in bottom two tracks.

Receptor Binding Domain (RBD) coverage

Supp. Fig. S72. Liu et al. (2019) PRJNA573298 samples Lung09 (SRR10168376), Lung08 (SRR10168377), Lung07 (SRR10168378) aligned to Pangolin CoV MP789 (MT121216.1) using bowtie2. RBD region highlighted.

Supp2 Fig2 S73. Lam et al. (2020) PRJNA606875 sample GD/P2S (SRR11093265) aligned to Pangolin CoV MP789 (MT121216.1) using bowtie2. RBD region highlighted.

Supp3 Fig. S74. Xiao et al. (2020) PRJNA606875 amplicon reads GD1 (SRR13053879) and sample A22 (SRR12053850) aligned to Pangolin CoV MP789 (MT121216.1) using bowtie2. RBD region highlighted.

Supp. Fig. S75. Liu et al. (2020) PRJNA686836 sample GZ1-2 (SRR13285085) aligned to Pangolin CoV MP789 (MT121216.1) using bowtie2. RBD region highlighted.

Supp. Fig. S76. 4 reads with end misalignment to MP789 in SRR10168375, indicated in strong colours. Aligned with bwa mem using default parameters

Supp. Fig. S77. Multiple reads misalign to MP789 at read ends in SRR10168377. Aligned with bwa mem using default parameters

Supp. Fig. S78. Multiple reads misalign to MP789 at read ends in SRR10168377 near the 5' end of the genome. Aligned with bwa mem using default parameters

Supp. Fig. S79. Multiple reads misalign to MP789 at read ends in SRR10168378. Aligned with bwa mem using default parameters